

FEDCSS: Efficient Bilevel Optimization for Joint Client-and-Sample Selection in Federated Learning

Anonymous submission

We have added the following experimental results.

1. Two more datasets, FEMNIST and CIFAR-100 in both i.i.d. and non-i.i.d. settings as illustrated in our manuscript. The noisy ratios are 0.4, 0.1.

Table 1: Test accuracy comparison for datasets FEMNIST and CIFAR-100.

Dataset	Setting	Test accuracy (%)						
		FedAvg	Loss-based	FOCUS	CAreFL	FocalLoss	ImpCSS	FEDCSS
FEMNIST	i.i.d.	99.20	98.23	99.04	98.54	98.22	98.31	99.56
	non-i.i.d. (1)	98.40	96.92	98.03	98.25	97.61	97.82	99.43
	non-i.i.d. (2)	99.10	96.51	97.31	97.82	97.14	97.02	99.51
CIFAR-100	i.i.d.	26.51	26.22	27.03	27.68	27.41	27.18	33.51
	non-i.i.d. (1)	25.27	24.92	26.17	26.83	27.01	26.67	32.42
	non-i.i.d. (2)	25.71	24.39	26.72	25.91	26.56	25.87	32.81

2. One new non-i.i.d. setting on MNIST and CIFAR-10 as in (McMahan et al. 2017), where there are at most 6 and 8 categories of samples in clients

Table 2: Test accuracy comparison under different non-i.i.d. settings.

Dataset	Setting	Test accuracy (%)						
		FedAvg	Loss-based	FOCUS	CAreFL	FocalLoss	ImpCSS	FEDCSS
MNIST	6	95.64	92.21	95.12	95.01	94.01	90.87	97.81
	8	96.75	93.86	96.93	96.80	95.65	93.2	98.68
CIFAR-10	6	41.16	38.96	41.02	41.72	40.26	40.82	44.23
	8	42.43	39.82	43.61	44.42	43.21	43.62	49.21

3. Reviewer 8: Large-scale simulations for CIFAR-10 with clients 100 to 500 with noisy ratio 0.4.

Table 3: Test accuracy comparison for large-scale simulations on CIFAR-10.

# clients	FedAvg	Loss-based	FOCUS	CAreFL	FocalLoss	ImpCSS	FEDCSS
100	38.76	38.98	39.12	40.21	40.01	39.82	45.73
200	37.25	37.86	37.93	39.80	39.65	38.2	44.85
300	35.19	35.92	35.82	36.32	37.21	36.89	41.64
400	33.92	32.96	33.61	34.82	33.71	33.12	39.52
500	31.62	30.83	31.80	33.96	32.01	31.08	37.17

4. Reviewer 8: We have added experiments by adopting the aggregation methods, FedLin (Mitra et al. 2021) and FedAvg, for all methods.

(1) Test accuracy of different methods by using FedLin aggregation method, which demonstrate the effectiveness of FEDCSS.

(2) Test accuracy of FEDCSS by using FedAvg aggregation method, while the results of other baselines are shown in Table 2 in the manuscript.

Table 4: Test accuracy comparison by using the FedLin aggregation method.

Dataset	Setting	Test accuracy (%)						
		FedAvg	Loss-based	FOCUS	CAreFL	FocalLoss	ImpCSS	FEDCSS
MNIST	i.i.d.	97.6	95.7	97.41	97.21	96.56	97.12	98.24
	non-i.i.d. (1)	96.13	94.38	95.02	97.19	95.17	95.28	98.36
	non-i.i.d. (2)	96.82	92.5	97.02	96.81	95.12	96.01	98.23
CIFAR-10	i.i.d.	48.43	42.71	48.56	49.02	48.91	48.72	53.73
	non-i.i.d. (1)	45.42	43.81	51.93	53.06	50.25	52.06	57.63
	non-i.i.d. (2)	47.63	43.92	48.06	43.74	42.81	42.84	53.55

Table 5: Test accuracy of FEDCSS by using the FedAvg aggregation method.

Dataset	Setting	Test accuracy (%)
MNIST	i.i.d.	98.08
	non-i.i.d. (1)	98.15
	non-i.i.d. (2)	98.06
CIFAR-10	i.i.d.	52.87
	non-i.i.d. (1)	56.69
	non-i.i.d. (2)	52.97

References

- McMahan, B.; Moore, E.; Ramage, D.; Hampson, S.; and y Arcas, B. A. 2017. Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data. In *Artificial intelligence and statistics*, 1273–1282. PMLR.
- Mitra, A.; Jaafar, R.; Pappas, G. J.; and Hassani, H. 2021. Linear convergence in federated learning: Tackling client heterogeneity and sparse gradients. *NeurIPS*, 34: 14606–14619.